

School Principals' Leadership Style and Work Performance of Teachers in Eastern Samar, Philippines

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Abstract:- This study determined the school heads' leadership styles and the work performance of teachers through individual performance commitment and review-based rating of the school they are assigned in Eastern Samar. A correlational research design was employed to address the primary aim of understanding the relationship between and among the variables of the study. A survey questionnaire was analyzed utilizing interquartile, range, median, and multiple hierarchical regression analysis at 0.05 level of significance. The findings revealed that school heads showed highly evident leadership styles, specifically transformational and laissez-faire approaches, while their teachers performed very satisfactory work performance. Further analysis revealed a significant predictability of combined leadership styles practiced by secondary school heads to that of teachers' level of work performance. It can be inferred a direct influence brought by various leadership styles in school. Therefore, extending the investigation to secondary school heads to validate the findings further.

Keywords:- *Laissez-Faire, Leadership Approaches, Transformational, Work Performance*

I. INTRODUCTION

According to Mosbarker (2009) a school head should possess and employ a range of leadership styles to effectively manage staff members with different qualities, attitudes, and professional needs. By utilizing a repertoire of leadership styles, school heads can adapt their staff members and create a conducive work environment. Leadership performance can be broadly categorized into several important phases. These trait theories assumed that successful leaders were born with a certain quality that set them apart from non-leaders. However, the challenge of categorizing and validating these traits led to widespread criticism of this approach, which in turn paved the way for style and behavioral approaches to leadership. The main finding of these studies suggests that leaders who adopt democracy tend to be more successful. This shift in emphasis highlighted the importance of leadership behavior and style in influencing performance outcomes.

Kenneth and Heresy (2020) an effective leader should possess good diagnostic leadership styles to meet the demands of the highlights of being flexible and responsive to the workplace. Advancements in technology and the recognition that employees can contribute more than just following orders and completing tasks have been an evolution in the understanding of leadership. Leaders are now realizing the benefits of incorporating the inputs and perspectives of their employees. The shift has led to a departure from traditional leadership forms, where decisions were solely based on the leader's expertise and perspectives. Instead, leaders are embracing a more diverse range of ideas and contributions from their team members.

The school efficiency is managed has a significant impact on the efficiency of employees and ultimately contributes to the achievement of organizational goals. When the schools prioritize and implement effective management practices, it creates an environment that fosters productivity, motivation, and job satisfaction among employees. If this is not carried out, the general performance of the employees suffers due to inappropriate leadership style. There is a lack of quality of learning among elementary and secondary schools in San Julian District, based on the result of the unified test conducted by the school Division Office of Eastern Samar-School Governance and Operations Division (SGOD) in School Year 2019-2020 in which the said District was tagged to be at the bottom five in the whole division for having low mean percentage Score (MPS) in the test. This can be associated with the leadership style practiced by the school needs. Effective leadership is needed to improve teachers' output rather than improving their performance.

II. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

This study aims to uncover the following research objectives;

- To determine the leadership styles employed by School Heads in the Division of Eastern Samar.
- To determine the level of work performance of secondary school teachers in the Division of Eastern Samar.
- To predict the level of work performance of secondary school teachers in terms of the leadership styles employed by school heads in the Division of Eastern Samar.

III. MATERIALS AND METHODS

➤ *Research design*

Correlation research design was employed to address the primary aim of understanding the relationship between and among the variables of the study. Initially, the study will use the descriptive aspect through the survey method to collect information on school heads' leadership styles as perceived by teachers and teachers' performance. Finally, it advanced to the correlation aspect to identify if the established models of leadership styles can predict the teacher's work performance.

➤ *Respondents and locale of the study*

The study was conducted in 20 secondary schools and a total of 50 respondents in the division of Eastern Samar. The researcher employed simple random sampling and filled out the survey questionnaire. A copy of their 2021 IPCRF was requested from the LIS coordinator.

➤ *Data collection method*

The first part dealt with the profile of the respondents. The second part was taken from a ready-made questionnaire on the Leadership Style of Bass and Avolio (1992) to measure the school heads' perception of their leadership styles and practices, as perceived by secondary school teachers, particularly on transformational leadership, transactional leadership, laissez faire leadership, and authoritative leadership. The researcher will make use of secondary data from the respondents' IPCR rating for the School Year 2020-2021.

➤ *Analysis of data*

Indicating that any observed effects or relationships with a probability of occurring by chance less than 5% would be considered statistically significant. The researcher made use of frequency count and percentage. Finally, the multiple

hierarchical regression analysis was employed to predict which model can significantly predict the criterion variable.

➤ *Ethical consideration*

The study adhered to the relevant research ethics guidelines, and consent forms were provided to the participants and collected accordingly. Additionally, a permit was obtained from the Schools Division Superintendent of Eastern Samar Division. The respondent was assured that their data would be treated confidentially.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

➤ *School heads' leadership style in Eastern Samar, Philippines*

Results show to determine the leadership styles in transformational, transactional, authoritative, laissez faire employed perceived by school teachers in division of Eastern Samar. The data was analyzed using the median and interquartile range, as shown in Table 1 below. Results from the analysis revealed that all four leadership styles are highly evident among school heads ($\bar{x} = 4$), with authoritative leadership having the highest measure of dispersion (IR = 2.313) while both transformational and Laissez Faire got the lowest interquartile range of 1 as perceived by their teachers. The result appears to support the notion of Smith and Squires (2016). School heads have more responsibilities on their administrative and instructional task such as creating an environment conducive to teaching and learning, innovating instructional materials, and encouraging faculty and staff development (Perez and Lumaad, 2021). The finding implies that the school administrator has a transformational and laissez-faire leadership. The participation of teachers and stakeholders in all programs and activities of the school has a great impact on the teaching-learning process.

Table 1. Leadership Style of School Heads

Leadership Styles	Median	Interquartile range	Interpretation
Transformational Leadership	4	1	Highly evident
Transactional Leadership	4	1.75	Highly evident
Authoritative Leadership	4	2.313	Highly evident
Laissez Faire Leadership	4	1	Highly evident

➤ *Secondary school teachers work performance in Eastern Samar, Philippines*

The second objective covers the level of work performance of the respondents as embedded in their approved 2020-2021 Individual Performance Commitment and Review rating on the four key result areas. The collected data were analyzed using frequency and percentage, as shown in Table 2. Results reveal that around 100% or 50 respondents acquired a very satisfactory rating. Similarly, Baluyos, et.al., (2019)

reported a very satisfactory performance rating of teacher-respondents in terms of the teaching-learning process, pupils' outcomes, community involvement, and professional growth. On the other hand, Salingkat (2017) the teachers' performance rating was low in teaching process evaluation. On an overall scale, teachers' level of work performance indicated that the teachers were able to carry their job very satisfactorily in the teaching-learning process, initiate activities that promote parents and community members' participation, and update

themselves through attending seminars, workshops, and conferences. Lastly, some technological advancements in

teaching to address academic issues and problems in the new normal.

Table 2. Level of work performance of secondary school teachers

Adjectival rating	Description	Frequency	Percent
3.500-4.499	Very Satisfactory	50	100
Total		50	100

➤ *Predictability of school heads’ leadership style toward teachers’ level of work performance in the division of Eastern Samar*

The last objective deals with analyzing the predictability of school head leadership styles and level of teachers' work performance in the Division of Eastern Samar. Four different models were derived with regression results shown in Table 3. The increasing value of r-squares from models 1 to 4 shows a sense of conducting hierarchical regression analysis. The four constructs, as seen in Model 4, described 24.50% of the teachers' level of work performance. The results on beta value per indicator show transactional leadership as a negative regressor to the teachers' work performance. Finally, two models referring to model 3 (R-square = .129; p-value = .018) and model 4 (R-square = .245; p-value = .012) both have shown significant regressions to that of the criterion variable.

This signifies that both models showing a combination of different leadership styles practiced by schools’ heads of secondary schools affect teachers’ work performance. The findings contradict Buenvenida and Ramos (2019) result since the combination of various leadership styles could not significantly influence the teachers' and students' performance. On the other hand, the findings share the same view as Nyenyembe et.al., (2016) the satisfaction of teachers was increased if they worked closely with their school head. Also, Saleem A. et.al., (2020) handled that the combinations of Four well-being outlined in the path–goal theory significantly predict teachers’ performance. Finally, the negative result on transactional leadership indicates that school heads who are not concerned with the needs of teachers and not involved in the educational processes, only reacting to disruptions in school, lead to less performing teachers.

Table 3. Multiple hierarchical regression analysis on the predictability of school heads’ leadership style toward teachers’ level of work performance in the division of Eastern Samar. $\alpha = .05$

Leadership Styles	R-square	B	p-value	Interpretation
Model 1 • Transformational Leadership	.015	.026	.392	Not significant
Model 2 • Transformational Leadership • Transactional Leadership	.016	.034	.880	Not significant
		-.008		
Model 3 • Transformational Leadership • Transactional Leadership • Authoritative Leadership	.129	.032	.018	Significant
		-.051		
		.069		
Model 4 • Transformational Leadership • Transactional Leadership • Authoritative Leadership • Laisses Faire Leadership	.245	.023	.012	Significant
		-.063		
		.051		
		.088		

V. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

To understand how different leadership styles may impact their work performance. It yielded several encouraging findings. The seeks to determine whether certain leadership approaches have a significant influence on the work performance of teachers. First, all four leadership styles, namely transformational, transactional, authoritative, and laissez faire are highly evident among school heads. However, it is noted that their perceptions are somehow highly dispersed in terms of authoritative leadership which implies that school heads are somehow moving out from the traditional approach to management. Second, the respondents have shown a very satisfactory level of work performance, despite the prevalence of pandemic and modular distance learning. Lastly, the combination of all the leadership styles employed by school heads significantly predicts the level of work performance of the respondents. Surprisingly, transactional leadership negatively impacts teachers' work performance despite the models.

Therefore, the reconceptualized and cultural setting will influence teachers' work performance outcomes. All these leads the researcher to recommend more stringent leadership training to be given to school heads, especially those that positively impact teachers' performance. Finally, this can be replicated using additional variables that can provide a different perspective and results.

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